

Strengthening Supervision of Leprosy Prevention and Control Activities in Colombo

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Background

- Regular, standard supervision is an essential part of effective prevention and control of leprosy.
- Supervision is vital to ensure program fidelity and detect weaknesses early.
- Formal supervisions with documented feedback on strengths, areas requiring improvement and recommendations are crucial for continued improvement.
- Structured supervision report formats ensure that all relevant aspects are addressed during a supervision, are documented and communicated.
- They also serve as evidence of district level supervisory activities and inform the National level.

Description of the intervention/initiative:

- A comprehensive supervision tool to assess all domains of leprosy prevention and control at Medical Officer of Health (MOH) level was developed.
- Expert inputs from Anti Leprosy Campaign were received to refine content.
- Nine key domains were identified.

Nine domains

- General information
- Documentation at MOH office (spot map, availability of registers)
- Individual patient data-tallied with notification registers and the national database
- Case surveillance and reporting
- Contact tracing and management
- Health education and awareness activities
- Staff capacity and training
- Community engagement and challenges
- Remarks and recommendations

Leprosy Checklist – MOH Visit (Colombo RDHS)

1. General Information

MOH Area: Name & Designation of Visiting Officer(s):	Date of Visit: Name & Designation of officers from whom information was gathered:
Average number of leprosy cases in the MOH area per year:	
No of PHI areas:	Available no of PHIs at present:
No of PHM areas:	Available no of PHMs at present:
General attitude of the MOH staff towards supervision:	

2. Documentation at MOH office

1. Spot Map

Availability of a spot map with leprosy cases marked – Yes No

When it was last updated –

2. Registers maintained at MOH office

	Notification Register	Contact tracing register	Suspected patients register
Maintained timely	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
By whom			
Completeness	All the columns filled Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
	Outcome mentioned Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
No of leprosy cases notified during the current year		Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
Are there any delays in giving to range PHI for investigation		Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>

3. Details of patients

No.	ALC No.	Name	Whether record in database	No. of record in notification register	No. of record in Contact Tracing Register	No. of total contacts screened at MOH	No. of total contacts referred	No. of contacts diagnosed as positive
1								
2								
3								
4								
5								
6								
7								
8								
9								
10								
11								
12								
13								
14								
15								

Figure 1- Supervision tool pages 1-2

4. Case Surveillance and Reporting

No. of cases reported from this MOH area in the current year	
No. of cases in WRCD	
No. of cases in RDHS level google sheet	
No. of cases in National database	
No. of active cases currently under treatment	
No. of defaulters and action taken	
No. of child cases	
No. of G2D	

5. Contact Tracing and Management

Are household contacts registered and screened? (Y/N)	
No. of contacts screened in current year	
Historical contact tracing	
Are there records of contact examination and follow-up?	

6. Health Education and Awareness Activities

No. of community awareness sessions held	
No. of schools covered in awareness sessions	
IEC materials used and distributed (specify type):	

7. Staff Capacity and Training

Have PHIs, PHNs, and MOH staff received leprosy training in the past year? (Y/N)	
No. of staff trained	
Are monthly review meetings conducted with field staff regarding leprosy? (Y/N)	

8. Community Engagement and Challenges

Are community leaders/volunteers engaged in case detection/awareness? (Y/N)	
Main challenges in leprosy control in the area:	
Action plan for next 3 months:	

9. Remarks and Recommendations

Any issues identified

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Suggestions for improvement

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Remarks by visiting officer

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Figure 1- Supervision tool pages 3-4

Methods used for the evaluation:

The utility of this supervision format was explored during the MOH supervision visits

Its feasibility in administration, ability to capture all relevant data and overall efficiency were assessed.

Results:

Improved structure and consistency in supervision across MOHs.

Since its introduction 7 MOH supervisions were completed with follow-up visits to assess progress.

All key programme components systematically reviewed.

Completed supervision reports were submitted to the national level through the recommended channels (Figure 2).

Enhanced efficiency — less time spent, more comprehensive outputs. (Figure 3 and 4).

The tool was sensitive to identify discrepancies in individual level data.

Positive feedback from MOH staff regarding clarity and usefulness.

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 කොළඹ දිස්ත්‍රික්කය
 பிராந்திய சுகாதார சேவை பணிப்பாளர் அலுவலகம்
 கொழும்பு மாவட்டம்

**REGIONAL DIRECTOR OF HEALTH SERVICES OFFICE
COLOMBO DISTRICT**

Director,
 Anti-leprosy Campaign,
 Welisara - Ragama.

Supervision reports on leprosy prevention and control

Following supervision reports related to leprosy prevention and control activities are herewith sent for your information.

- 1) MOH Office Boresalgamuwa
- 2) MOH Office Egodaunya
- 3) MOH Office Homagama

Dr. Muditha Karunathilaka
 Consultant Leprologist - Section
 Deputy Regional Director of Health Services
 Colombo

Regional Director of Health Services,
Colombo.

Cc: 1. Deputy Director General (PHS) I, Ministry of Health
2. Provincial Director of Health Services, Western Province

ලේකම් Director (+9411 2327893)	අධ්‍යක්ෂ Assistant Director (+9411 2402027)	ප්‍රධාන අධ්‍යක්ෂ Chief Executive Officer (+9411 2407710)	අධ්‍යක්ෂ Director (+9411 2302348)
ලේකම් Director (+9411 2321256)	අධ්‍යක්ෂ Assistant Director (+9411 2402020)	ප්‍රධාන අධ්‍යක්ෂ Chief Executive Officer (+9411 2407710)	අධ්‍යක්ෂ Director (+9411 2302348)

Figure 2- Supervision Reports sent as official communications

Leprosy Checklist – MOH Visit (Colombo RDHS)

1. General Information

MOH Area: <u>Boresalgamuwa</u>	Date of Visit: <u>21.07.2025</u>
Name & Designation of Visiting Officer(s): <u>Consultant Community Physician (Regional Epidemiologist)</u> <u>Medical Officer Epidemiology</u>	Name & Designation of officers from whom information was gathered: <u>Dr. Sanjeewa (AMOH)</u> <u>Mr. Sanjeewa (SPHI)</u> <u>Mr. MH Gananayake (PH3)</u>
Average number of leprosy cases in the MOH area per year: <u>4</u>	
No of PHI areas: <u>6</u>	Available no of PHIs at present: <u>6</u>
No of PHM areas: <u>12</u>	Available no of PHMs at present: <u>11</u>
General attitude of the MOH staff towards supervision: <u>Satisfactory</u>	

2. Documentation at MOH office

1. Spot Map
Availability of a spot map with leprosy cases marked – Yes No
When it was last updated –

2. Registers maintained at MOH office

	Notification Register	Contact tracing register	Suspected patients register
Maintained timely	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
By whom			
Completeness	All the columns filled: Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Outcome mentioned: Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
No of leprosy cases notified during the current year	<u>4</u>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Are there any delays in giving to range PHI for investigation	<u>No</u>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

MOH Area: Egoda Uyana

Date of Visit: 11.07.2025

Name & Designation of Visiting Officer(s):
Medical Officer Epidemiology

Name & Designation of officers from whom information was gathered:
Dr. Danaraji (AMOH)
Mr. D.B. Mawssava (SPHI)
Mr. R.D.M.P. Kumarsinghe (PH3)

Average number of leprosy cases in the MOH area per year: 20

No of PHI areas: 9

No of PHM areas: 19

Available no of PHIs at present: 9

Available no of PHMs at present: 23

General attitude of the MOH staff towards supervision: Satisfactory

2. Documentation at MOH office

1. Spot Map
Availability of a spot map with leprosy cases marked – Yes No
When it was last updated – updated.

2. Registers maintained at MOH office

	Notification Register	Contact tracing register	Suspected patients register
Maintained timely	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
By whom	<u>SPHI</u>	<u>SPHI/PHI</u>	<u>SPHI/PHI</u>
Completeness	All the columns filled: Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Outcome mentioned: Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
No of leprosy cases notified during the current year	<u>20</u>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Are there any delays in giving to range PHI for investigation	<u>No</u>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Figure 3- Supervision Reports from MOH Egoda Uyana and Boalesgamwa

9. Remarks and Recommendations

Any issues identified

- No major deficiencies were noted

Suggestions for improvement

- To expedite the hybrid Gantt training activity. As the period of 2016-2021 (lists have been sent)

Remarks by visiting officer

- To strengthen the current Gantt activities
- A follow-up visit is planned in 3/12

on behalf of the team

[Signature]
Dr P.K. Buddhika Mahesh
(MBS, MSc, MD)
Consultant Community Physician
Regional Epidemiologist
Office of Regional Director of Health Services
Colombo

9. Remarks and Recommendations

Any issues identified

- This is the main area with the highest leprosy burden

Suggestions for improvement

- Many of the same identified in the previous report by Dr. Mc have been addressed

Remarks by visiting officer

- A follow-up visit has been planned to be done in 1/12

on behalf of the district team

[Signature]
Dr P.K. Buddhika Mahesh
(MBS, MSc, MD)
Consultant Community Physician
Regional Epidemiologist
Office of Regional Director of Health Services
Colombo

(This supervision was not attended by me. But I will be attending the follow up supervision)
C/P/A

9. Remarks and Recommendations

Any issues identified

- No major deficiencies identified

Suggestions for improvement

- To expedite the hybrid Gantt training. As the period 2016-2021

Remarks by visiting officer

- A follow-up visit is planned in 3/12

on behalf of the team

[Signature]
Dr P.K. Buddhika Mahesh
(MBS, MSc, MD)
Consultant Community Physician
Regional Epidemiologist
Office of Regional Director of Health Services
Colombo

Figure 4- Observations and remarks by Regional Epidemiologist

Lessons learnt:

- The introduction of a structured standard supervision tool to evaluate leprosy prevention and control activities is both an effective and efficient.
- Standardized supervision tools ensure objectivity and completeness.
- Documentation improves accountability and supports national monitoring.
- Collaboration between national, district, and MOH levels is essential.

THANK YOU

COLOMBO RDHS